

Università degli Studi di Cagliari
Dipartimento di Scienze Chimiche e Geologiche
prof. Vito Lippolis

Monserrato (CA), February 2022

Confirmation Letter

I had the opportunity to know Dr. Mattia Nieddu before 2013 as project student for the Master degree in Chemistry. Throughout his duration Mattia worked exceptionally hard, diligently and effectively. In 2016 he started the PhD at the University of Cagliari in Cotutela with the University of la Rioja under the supervision of myself and Prof. José Maria López-de-Luzuriaga. During this time, he was concerning the synthesis, characterization and study of luminescent Au/Ag and Au/Tl heterometallic compounds with mixed donor macrocyclic derivatives. For all these reasons, I confirm that Dr. Nieddu has made the experimental work (synthesis, characterization, etc.) during his bachelor/Master thesis for publications shown here:

C., Bazzicalupi, C., Caltagirone, Z., Cao, Q., Chen, C., Di Natale, A., Garau, V., Lippolis*, L., Lvova, H., Liu, I., Lundström, M. C., Mostallino, **M.**, Nieddu, R., Paolesse*, L., Prodi, M., Sgarzi N., Zaccheroni*: Multimodal use of new coumarin-based fluorescent chemosensors: towards highly selective optical sensors for Hg²⁺ probing. *Chemistry - A European Journal*, 2013, 19, 14639.

Signed
Prof. Vito Lippolis

Confirmation Letter

I had the opportunity to know Dr. Mattia Nieddu in 2016 when he started his PhD between the University of Cagliari and my laboratory in university of la Rioja under the supervision of myself and Prof. Vito Lippolis. During this time, he was concerned with the synthesis, characterization and study of luminescent Au/Ag and Au/Tl heterometallic compounds with mixed donor macrocyclic derivatives. For all these reasons, I confirm that Dr. Nieddu has made the experimental work (synthesis, characterization, etc.) for the publications shown here:

1. Donamaría, R., Lippolis, V.,* López-de-Luzuriaga, J. M.,* Monge, **M.**, **Nieddu**, M., Olmos, M. E.*: Optical Properties in Heteronuclear Gold(I)/Silver(I) Complexes of Aliphatic Mixed Donor Macrocycles Featuring Metallophilic Interactions. *European Journal of Inorganic Chemistry*, **2021**, 44, 4552.
2. Donamaría, R., Lippolis, V.,* López-de-Luzuriaga, J. M.,* Monge, M., **Nieddu**, **M.**, Olmos, M. E.*: Metallophilic Au(I)...M(I) interactions (M = Tl, Ag) in heteronuclear complexes with 1,4,7-triazacyclononane: structural features and optical properties. *Dalton Transactions*, **2020**, 49, 10983.
3. Donamaría, R., Lippolis, V.,* López-de-Luzuriaga, J. M.,* Monge, **M.**, **Nieddu**, M., Olmos, M. E.*: Structural and luminescence properties of heteronuclear Gold(I)/Thallium(I) complexes featuring metallophilic interactions tuned by quinoline pendant arm derivatives of mixed donor macrocycles. *Inorganic Chemistry*, **2020**, 59, 6398.
4. Donamaría, R., Lippolis, V.,* López-de-Luzuriaga, J. M.,* Monge, **M.**, **Nieddu**, M., Olmos, M. E.*: Dispersive forces and dipole moment increase as driving forces for the formation of an unprecedented metallophilic heterotrimetallic system. *Chemistry - A European Journal*, **2018**, 24, 13740.
5. Donamaría, R., Lippolis, V.,* López-de-Luzuriaga, J. M.,* Monge, **M.**, **Nieddu**, M., Olmos, M. E.*: Influence of the number of metallophilic interactions and structures on the optical properties of heterometallic Au/Ag complexes with mixed-donor macrocyclic ligands. *Inorganic Chemistry*, **2018**, 57, 11099.
6. Donamaría, R., Lippolis, V.,* López-de-Luzuriaga, J. M.,* Monge, **M.**, **Nieddu**, M., Olmos, M. E.*: Tuning Au(I)···Tl(I) interactions via mixed thia-aza macrocyclic ligands: effects on the structural and luminescence properties. *Inorganic Chemistry*, **2017**, 56, 12551.

Prof. Dr. José Mª López de Luzuriaga
(Chemistry Department. University of La Rioja)